

Strategic Communication Enhancement through Private Language Modelling

Jayashree Piri^{#1}, Pragyana Paramita Das^{#2}, Nikhil Agrawal^{#3}, Kajal Sharma^{#4}, Urjja Banka^{#5}, Raghunath Dey^{*6}

^{#12345} Dept. of CSE, Silicon University, Bhubaneswar, India

^{*6} School of Computer Engineering, KIIT Deemed to be University, Bhubaneswar, India

Abstract— In recent years, the invention of large language models, such as Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT), has revolutionized various fields, from natural language processing to content generation. However, as organizations are relying on AI technologies to drive innovation and efficiency, concerns surrounding data privacy and ethical AI practices have become normal. In response to these challenges, private GPT models have emerged as a promising solution, offering a novel approach to protect sensitive data while upholding ethical principles within organizational settings. This paper provides an in-depth exploration of private GPT models, delving into their technical underpinnings, benefits, challenges, and ethical considerations. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature and case studies, we explain the significance of private GPT models in ensuring data privacy, confidentiality, and fairness. Furthermore, we discuss the implications of adopting private GPT models for organizational decision-making, user experiences, and societal well-being. This paper aims to inform researchers, practitioners, and policymakers about the importance of integrating privacy-enhancing technologies into AI systems and fostering a culture of responsible AI development. Chat GPT is not just an AI tool but it is upcoming future in Software Engineering. Private GPT not only ensures security of data but also makes the work easier for the workers of the organization to minimize their work.

Keywords- Large Language Models (LLMs), Cosine Similarity, Keyword Search, Vectorized Document Database, Prompt based, Flask.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) [1] into various aspects of our lives has become increasingly prevalent. One such remarkable innovation is the development of ChatGPT [2], a communication tool crafted by Open AI, leveraging the power of AI language models to facilitate seamless interactions between humans and computers. This ground breaking technology has revolutionized the way we communicate, enabling us to converse with machines in a natural and intuitive manner.

As educational institutions strive to adapt to the evolving landscape of technology, the need for efficient and accessible communication channels has become more pronounced than ever. Colleges and universities serve as hubs of learning and information dissemination, catering to the diverse needs of students, faculty, administrative staff, and parents alike. However, navigating the complexities of academic life, such as admissions, fees, placements, and other administrative processes, can often be time consuming. At its core, the private GPT model [3] being developed for Silicon University (SU) serves as a virtual assistant, capable of understanding and responding to a wide range of queries related to admissions, academic programs, campus facilities, events, and more. Whether it's a prospective student inquiring about the application process, a parent seeking information about tuition fees, or a faculty member looking for administrative support, the private GPT interface will serve as a reliable and accessible point of contact.

Moreover, the implementation of a private GPT communication tool aligns with SIT's commitment to fostering transparency, accessibility, and innovation in education. By leveraging AI technology, we aim to bridge communication gaps, streamline administrative processes, and enhance the overall experience of students and stakeholders within the college community.

Fig. 1 chatGPT

Fig.1 [4] shows the various aspects of chatGPT. In this paper, we embark on a comprehensive exploration of the rationale, development process, functionalities, and potential impact of the private GPT model for Silicon University (SU) Bhubaneswar. We delve into the technical intricacies of AI language models, the challenges and considerations inherent in designing a private communication tool, and the ethical implications of deploying AI in educational settings. Furthermore, we discuss the broader implications of this initiative for the future of communication and engagement within academic institutions, envisioning a landscape where AI-powered solutions [5] foster collaboration, efficiency, and inclusivity.

Through this pioneering initiative, SU endeavours to set a precedent for leveraging AI technology to enhance the educational experience, empower stakeholders, and promote a culture of innovation and excellence. Join us on this transformative journey as we harness the power of private GPT to redefine communication and engagement in higher education.

II. NEED FOR CHATGPT IN EDUCATION SECTOR

In the realm of education, where seamless communication and accessibility are paramount, the advent of ChatGPT emerges as a beacon of innovation and inclusivity. With its intuitive interface and instant responses, ChatGPT revolutionizes the way students, parents, and educators will interact with educational institutions. This virtual assistant [6], available at the fingertips of users, transcends the confines of traditional communication channels, offering personalized assistance and support round-the-clock. From inquiries about admissions procedures to guidance on coursework and extracurricular activities, it will serve as a trusted companion, empowering stakeholders to navigate the complexities of academic with ease and confidence. Moreover, its multilingual capabilities ensure that language barriers are no longer a hindrance, fostering inclusivity and accessibility for diverse communities. As schools embrace ChatGPT, they not only streamline administrative processes and reduce workload but also foster a culture of open communication, engagement, and collaboration within the educational ecosystem. Here are some areas where the private ChatGPT can be used:

Educate Students: Students may not have much knowledge about the college when they are in their first year, they can use this GPT for their various queries and doubts regarding the college. Students may educate themselves with their queries and gain knowledge on various fields.

Accessing Information about Faculties and rules handbook: This GPT may help to retrieve questions and queries regarding the faculties' information. Rules and protocols are followed in every college so this GPT [15] may guide the students on their queries.

Retrieve information regarding Placement statistics: This GPT will store data for the college database and can provide information regarding the placement statistics for each year.

Access information after uploading any document: This GPT has an additional feature where we can upload any document in pdf format and can ask any questions related to the document without doing any scrolling in the pdf. This feature helps make retrieval easier without scrolling through the document.

Provide Suggestions and Counselling: The GPT not only gives the website information data but also gives suggestions about the college various amenities like canteen facilities, food, transport system etc. It provides accurate information regarding the college for you to decide whether you want to join college or not.

Educate faculties and parents: This GPT will provide information to faculties regarding the college and various fields. The parents will also get their queries resolved about the college and the atmosphere of college.

The faculties may use this GPT when they are new to college that how this college works.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Investigate Private GPT Models: To explore the technical aspects, benefits, challenges, and ethical considerations associated with private Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) models [7].

Examine Data Privacy and Ethical AI Practices: To analyse the concerns surrounding data privacy and ethical AI practices in organizations and assess how private GPT models address these challenges.

Evaluate Significance of Private GPT Models: To assess the significance of private GPT models [3] in ensuring data privacy, confidentiality, and fairness, through a comprehensive review of existing literature and case studies.

Discuss Implications for Organizational Decision- Making: To discuss the implications of adopting private GPT models for organizational decision-making processes [8], user experiences, and societal well-being.

Inform Stakeholders: To inform researchers, practitioners, and policymakers about the importance of integrating privacy-enhancing technologies into AI systems and fostering responsible AI development practices.

Explore Application in Educational Settings: To investigate the application of private GPT models in educational settings, focusing on their potential to streamline communication processes and enhance stakeholder engagement within colleges and universities.

Examine Technical Development and Functionality: To delve into the technical intricacies of developing a private GPT-based communication tool, exploring its functionalities and capabilities as a virtual assistant for academic inquiries and administrative support.

Assess Impact on Higher Education: To assess the potential impact of implementing private GPT models in higher education institutions, envisioning a landscape where AI- powered solutions [9] foster collaboration, efficiency, and inclusivity in academic settings.

Set a Precedent for AI Integration in Education: To document the rationale, development process, and potential impact of implementing a private GPT model for Silicon University (SU), aiming to set a precedent for leveraging AI technology to enhance the educational Experience and promote innovation in communication and engagement within academic institutions.

IV. SIGNIFICANT WORKFLOW DIMENSIONS OF CHATGPT FOR EDUCATION SECTOR

Fig. 2 Workflow diagram of chatGPT

The details of each step is given below:

1. Understanding GPT Architecture

The first step in creating private ChatGPT is to gain a deep understanding of the underlying architecture of GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) models. This involves studying the following key aspects:

Transformer Model: GPT is based on the transformer model, which uses self-attention mechanisms to process input data and generate outputs. Understanding how transformers work, including concepts like attention heads and positional encodings, was essential.

Pre-training and Fine-tuning: GPT models are pre-trained on large text corpora using unsupervised learning. After pre-training, the models are fine-tuned on specific datasets for targeted tasks.

Layers and Parameters: Understanding the number of layers, parameters, and other hyper parameters that define the model's capacity and performance.

2. Choosing a Framework

After understanding the architecture, the next step is, selecting a framework for implementation. This decision is influenced by:

Flexibility: How easily the framework can adapt to different tasks and modifications.

Community Support: Availability of community resources, tutorials, and forums for troubleshooting and development.

Integration: Ease of integrating with other tools and libraries needed for your project.

Two popular frameworks were considered: TensorFlow: Known for its robustness and extensive community support. PyTorch: Valued for its flexibility and ease of use, particularly for research and development.

3. Extraction of Data

High-quality data is critical for training a conversational AI model. The steps involved are:

Sourcing Data: Identifying relevant datasets that contain examples of conversations. This includes both publicly available datasets and proprietary data.

Web Scraping: Extracting data from specific websites like Silicon using web scraping techniques. This involves writing scripts to automatically gather and save data from web pages.

Ensuring Diversity and Relevance: Making sure the datasets are diverse and relevant to the use cases the AI model will address.

4. Preprocessing of Data

Raw data needs to be transformed into a suitable format for training. This includes:

Tokenization: Breaking down text into smaller units (tokens), such as words or sub words, which the model can process.

Cleaning: Removing noise, such as HTML tags, special characters, and irrelevant sections.

Normalization: Standardizing text to a consistent format, including lowercasing and handling punctuation.

5. Building the User Interface: Developing the user interface (UI) is crucial for providing a seamless interaction experience:

Design: Creating an intuitive and user-friendly interface that users can interact with easily using HTML, CSS and JAVASCRIPT.

Functionality: Ensuring the UI allows users to input queries and view responses effortlessly.

User Engagement: Implementing features that enhance user engagement, such as response suggestions, feedback options, and personalization settings.

6. Building the LLM Model

The core of your ChatGPT is its Language Model (LLM), which involved:

Framework Implementation: Using the chosen framework to build and configure the model.

Training: Fine-tuning a pre-trained GPT model on your specific conversational datasets to tailor it to your needs. Pre-trained models from resources like Hugging Face are utilized to expedite this process.

Hyper parameter Tuning: Adjusting model parameters to optimize performance.

7. Evaluating Performance

Post-training, the model's performance needed to be rigorously evaluated:

Metrics: Using metrics such as perplexity (a measure of how well the model predicts the next word in a sentence), fluency, and coherence.

Testing: Running the model through various scenarios to assess its ability to generate contextually relevant and coherent responses.

Iteration: Iteratively refining the model based on evaluation results to improve its performance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integration of ChatGPT, a private GPT-based communication tool, into educational settings represents a significant step towards leveraging AI technology to enhance communication. The emergence of private GPT models addresses critical concerns surrounding data privacy and ethical AI practices. With the increasing reliance on AI technologies in educational institutions, safeguarding sensitive data and ensuring confidentiality are paramount. Private GPT models offer a novel solution by providing a secure environment for communication and information exchange, thereby mitigating the risks associated with data breaches and privacy violations. By incorporating privacy-enhancing technologies into AI systems, educational institutions can uphold ethical principles and build trust among students, faculty, and other stakeholders. Creating a customized version of ChatGPT for our organization involves several key technologies and processes.

Let's outline the steps and technologies involved:

Natural Language Processing (NLP) Technology: NLP forms the foundation of ChatGPT, enabling it to understand and generate human-like text. **Process:** Utilize pre-trained NLP models, such as OpenAI's GPT, as the core engine for understanding and generating responses.

Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning Technology: ML and deep learning techniques [13] are employed for training and fine-tuning the NLP models. **Process:** Train the NLP model on large datasets of

text to learn patterns and relationships, and fine-tune it on domain-specific data relevant to your organization, such as educational materials or FAQs.

Web Development Technology: Web development frameworks and languages (e.g., HTML, CSS, JavaScript) are used to create the user interface for interacting with ChatGPT. **Process:** Develop a user-friendly web interface where users can input queries and receive responses from ChatGPT. Ensure compatibility across different devices and browsers.

API Integration Technology: RESTful APIs or GraphQL [14] can be used to integrate ChatGPT with other systems or platforms. **Process:** Create APIs that allow seamless integration of ChatGPT with existing organizational systems, such as learning management systems (LMS), student portals, or administrative databases.

Data Annotation and Preparation Technology: Annotation tools and data pre-processing libraries (e.g., spaCy, NLTK) are utilized for data preparation. **Process:** Curate and annotate datasets relevant to your organization's domain to train and fine-tune the NLP model. This may include transcripts of past interactions, educational materials, or FAQs.

Deployment and Hosting Technology: Cloud computing platforms (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud, Azure) are commonly used for deployment. **Process:** Deploy ChatGPT on a cloud server to ensure scalability and accessibility. Configure load balancing and monitoring to manage traffic and performance.

Continuous Improvement Technology: Version control systems (e.g. Git) and automated testing frameworks are utilized for continuous improvement. **Process:** Implement a feedback loop where user interactions with ChatGPT are analysed to identify areas for improvement. Regularly update and retrain the model based on new data and user feedback.

Security and Compliance Technology: Encryption protocols, access controls, and compliance frameworks (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA) are implemented to ensure data security and privacy. **Process:** Adhere to best practices for securing user data and complying with relevant regulations and standards, especially when handling sensitive information within educational contexts. By leveraging these technologies and following a systematic development process, your organization can create a tailored version of ChatGPT that meets the specific needs and objectives of your educational institution.

The creation of a private GPT for SU has yielded significant results, primarily centered on enhancing communication and information exchange. By leveraging AI technology [16], we have established a secure and efficient platform that enables seamless interactions between stakeholders. The integration of private GPT models addresses critical concerns surrounding data privacy and ethical AI practices, ensuring the confidentiality of sensitive information. As a result, users experience improved accessibility, personalized support, and enhanced efficiency in accessing educational resources and administrative services. Furthermore, the scalability and adaptability of the private GPT platform enable seamless integration with existing systems and workflows, paving the way for future advancements in educational communication and collaboration. The details of the output is shown below:

Fig. 3: Uploading the files

A screenshot of a terminal window with a dark background. At the top, there are tabs for 'PROBLEMS', 'OUTPUT', 'PORTS', 'TERMINAL', and 'DEBUG CONSOLE'. The 'TERMINAL' tab is active. The text in the terminal shows a query: 'What are the Roles and Responsibilities of CoE?'. Below it, the response is displayed, starting with '> Answer:'. The response text describes the roles and responsibilities of the Controller of Examinations (CoE) in seven numbered points. At the bottom of the terminal, there is a prompt 'Enter a query:' followed by a cursor.

```
PROBLEMS OUTPUT PORTS TERMINAL DEBUG CONSOLE python + v [ ] [ ] ... ^ X

What are the Roles and Responsibilities of CoE?

> Answer:
Based on the provided context, the roles and responsibilities of the Controller of Examinations (CoE) are as follows:
1. Monitoring Semester Registration: The CoE ensures that all students register for their respective semesters according to the academic regulation and calendar.
2. Monitoring Examination Registration: The CoE verifies that all eligible students register for their examinations as per the approved timetable.
3. Preparing Admit Cards for eligible students: The CoE prepares admit cards for students who are eligible to appear in examinations.
4. Assigning responsibilities to Examination Committee members: The CoE assigns tasks and roles to the Examination Committee members to ensure smooth conduct of all examination processes.
5. Evaluation of Answer Scripts: The CoE is responsible for evaluating answer scripts and declaring results.
6. Post-processing of Results: The CoE provides additional time to examiners depending on the number of answer scripts to be evaluated, and declares the results usually within three to four weeks from the date of the last examination.
7. Other responsibilities: The CoE may give additional duties as per requirement.
It is important to note that the Deputy/Assistant Controller(s) of Examinations may also be appointed by the Principal to assist the CoE in discharging their roles and responsibilities.

Enter a query: |
```

Fig. 4: Response from a given query

VI. CONCLUSION

In navigating the ever-expanding realms of technology, the journey towards fostering transparent and inclusive communication within academic institutions like Silicon University is both a challenge and an opportunity. Through the development and implementation of a private GPT-based communication tool, SIT has embarked on a path of innovation aimed at enhancing the educational experience for students, faculty, staff, and parents alike. The journey towards creating this tool has not been without its complexities. From technical intricacies to ethical considerations, SIT has navigated a landscape fraught with challenges. However, through perseverance and a steadfast commitment to responsible AI development [17], the institution has emerged with a solution that holds immense promise.

The private GPT model developed for SU stands as more than just a virtual assistant; it embodies the values of transparency, accessibility, and innovation that the institution holds dear. By leveraging AI technology, SU has succeeded in bridging communication gaps, streamlining administrative processes, and enhancing the overall experience of its stakeholders.

Looking ahead, the implications of this initiative extend far beyond the confines of the institution. As AI-powered solutions continue to proliferate, the potential for collaboration, efficiency, and inclusivity within academic settings grows exponentially. SU's pioneering efforts serve as a beacon of inspiration for educational institutions worldwide, illustrating the transformative power of AI in shaping the future of communication and engagement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Oliveira, J. S. D., & Neves, I. B. S. (2023). Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT and Organizational Studies. *Organizações & Sociedade*, 30, 388-400.
- [2] Roumeliotis, K. I., & Tselikas, N. D. (2023). Chatgpt and open-ai models: A preliminary review. *Future Internet*, 15(6), 192.
- [3] Krause, D. (2023). ChatGPT and Other AI Models as a Due Diligence Tool: Benefits and Limitations for Private Firm Investment Analysis. Available at SSRN 4416159.
- [4] <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2023/03/01/the-best-examples-of-what-you-can-do-with-chatgpt/?sh=2901f821df11>
- [5] Fui-Hoon Nah, F., Zheng, R., Cai, J., Siau, K., & Chen, L. (2023). Generative AI and ChatGPT: Applications, challenges, and AI-human collaboration. *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research*, 25(3), 277-304.
- [6] Hacker, P., Engel, A., & Mauer, M. (2023, June). Regulating ChatGPT and other large generative AI models. In *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (pp. 1112-1123).
- [7] Aydin, Ö., & Karaarslan, E. (2023). Is ChatGPT leading generative AI? What is beyond expectations?. *Academic Platform Journal of Engineering and Smart Systems*, 11(3), 118-134.
- [8] Frieder, S., Pinchetti, L., Griffiths, R. R., Salvatori, T., Lukasiewicz, T., Petersen, P., & Berner, J. (2024). Mathematical capabilities of chatgpt. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36.
- [9] Ortiz, S. (2023). What is ChatGPT and why does it matter? Here's what you need to know. ZDNET.
- [10] Lopes, C. V., Klotzman, V. I., Ma, I., & Ahmed, I. (2024). Commit Messages in the Age of Large Language Models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.17622.
- [11] De Silva, A., Wijekoon, J. L., Liyanarachchi, R., Panchendrarajan, R., & Rajapaksha, W. (2024). AI Insights: A Case Study on Utilizing ChatGPT Intelligence for Research Paper Analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.03293.
- [12] Leiter, C., Zhang, R., Chen, Y., Belouadi, J., Larionov, D., Fresen, V., & Eger, S. (2024). Chatgpt: A meta-analysis after 2.5 months. *Machine Learning with Applications*, 16, 100541.
- [13] Johnson, S., Owens, E., Menendez, H., & Kim, D. (2024). Using ChatGPT-generated essays in library instruction. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2), 102863.
- [14] D'Amato, K. (2024). ChatGPT: towards AI subjectivity. *AI & SOCIETY*, 1-15.
- [15] Xu, Z., Jain, S., & Kankanhalli, M. (2024). Hallucination is inevitable: An innate limitation of large language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.11817.
- [16] So, A. (2024). The implications of ethical perspectives in AI and autonomous systems. In *Ethics in Online AI-based Systems* (pp. 135-152). Academic Press.
- [17] Leaua, C., Conte, L., Leaua, G., & Demarchi, J. (2024). The Art of Questioning: Redefining the Value of Interrogative Communication in the Era of AI. Available at SSRN 4707665.